

The Impact of Brand Extension on Brand Personality a Case Study of Nestle Pakistan

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Abstract

This research study is to test the impact of Brand Extension on Brand Personality of the brand Nestle, Pakistan. Brand extension is usually done for the well reputed brands, who serve as an umbrella for success of other brands and their products. The variables related to brand extension taken into consideration for this study include the competitive strategy, quality, perceived fit, innovation, and brand loyalty. Data for this study was gathered using primary sources. The instrument used for gathering primary data was the close-ended questionnaire, which was self-administered from a sample of 214 consumers of Nestle. The analysis of the data collected reveals that brand personality does get impact through brand extension. All five variables of brand extension have a significant impact on brand personality. Recommendations are also made for the organization(s) to take advantage of brand extension for future launch of products.

Keywords: Brand Personality, Brand Extension, Competitive Strategy, Quality, Perceived Fit, Innovation, Brand Loyalty.

Introduction

A brand extension comprises using a well-known brand name to extend into a new product in a separate or related area. Given the high startup costs for new brands, brand extension can be a useful strategy for a new product's cost-effective introduction. Clients and marketers alike benefit from being familiar with an established brand. Customers apply the traits associated with the old brand to the new brand. The newest product on the market is more quickly accepted (Hameed, Soomro, Kaimkhani, & Shakoor, 2013).

To explore how brand extension affects brand personality in Pakistan's competitive market today. Maintaining a brand's personality during an extension is extremely difficult. Successful brand extensions aid companies in gaining market share and expanding their product offerings. They might give the company an advantage over competitors who do not offer comparable products. The well-known brand serves as an effective and reasonably priced marketing tool for the new product. Because brand image and brand perception are affected by brand extensions, this research will not consider Nestlé's energy as a brand after launching many brand extensions or whether the brand expansions were coherent in nature or not.

Brand Personality

A strong and consistent brand image, or a group of connections that the brand strategist aims to create or maintain, is essential for a successful brand. Unlike brand name, brand image conveys the values that the corporation wants the brand to stand for. The identity prism is a conglomeration of six dimensions, including brand personality, brand community, customer interactions, reflection, personality, and self-perception. The brand's identity is a representation of the relationships that people have with it. Each brand has a unique culture that is characterized by certain characteristics. Therefore, it is appropriate to view brands as a collection of

values. Values are fundamental ideas that direct a brand's behavior. The brand is seen as an active, collaborative partner in the commitment that takes place between a person and the brand. Customers' relationships with brands determine their success (Abdavi & Shiralizadeh, 2015).

The collection of human features that are often linked with a brand is referred to as the consumer's image. By remaining loyal to a brand, consumers are given the chance to talk about that brand with their friends and family. The brand's physical attributes that are perceived by our senses are related to the brand's physical appearance. Self-image is the process by which a brand aids a customer in revising a personal statement. The three most crucial elements of brand identity, brand values, relationships, and user image are based on the brand personality (Buil & Hem, 2009).

Brand identity has both personal and social components, with the former being characterized by relationships and user perception and the latter by brand personality and brand values. A newly launched product belonging to a completely different category may be consistent with either the social dimension (i.e., relationships and user image) or the personal dimension (i.e., brand personality and brand values) of brand identity when compared to products typically marketed under a well-known brand identity (Viot, 2011).

Branding and brand management are widely used in marketing. A brand is a system that buyers and sellers have long been connected to; brand plays a big part in creating that relationship. According to mass producers who strive to manufacture a product category or the same service, customers rely on the brand when making purchasing selections. Many businesses want to build a powerful brand in their sector (Alavinasab, Soltani & Alimohammadi 20017).

A brand is a name, word, symbol, logo, or design, alone or in combination, which is used to distinguish and set apart the products and services of a vendor or group of vendors from those of rivals. Shoppers must make selections during the shopping process and have options due to the variety of goods available. Additionally, businesses found that acquiring new consumers costs five times more than keeping their current ones. In today's competitive markets, holding consumers, growing market share, and constructing, retaining, and promoting a brand are the key issues of businesses that demand the most precise technical skill of marketers (Donald, 2011).

An important cost is attached to the launch of a new brand on the market. Therefore, a brand's capacity to facilitate consumer decision-making, lower risk, and determine their preferences is priceless. These days, the most popular strategies for fostering business growth include brand extension strategies and the expansion of customer preferences to other commodities. The use of a brand that has a license for one product category in a different product category is known as brand extension. It enables a product to develop acceptability and a reputation among customers very quickly (Ergin & Sahin 2015).

The cost of promoting these products and services is not very high. Marketers presume that consumers view brands as extremely desirable in many circumstances, thus consumers extend the positive attributes and sensations of the primary brand they are thinking of to two supplementary products. Therefore, instead of developing a new brand, companies continue to utilize one of their existing ones in new markets (a practice known as brand extension). In today's competitive markets, a business must keep its consumers and increase its sales because keeping existing customers costs less than obtaining new ones. (Corsi, Dawes, Driensener & Sharp, 2019).

Brand Extension

Brand extensions frequently present a chance to establish superiority over a freely selected purchasing criterion. Unexpectedly, the differentiation of a brand extension is simpler because it is simpler to focus on the target market and identify competitors. Brand extensions ought to innovate to beat their rivals. To avoid giving clients common cues about a category, a fundamental analysis of a product is always appropriate (Hadi & Sandu, 2020).

A trip to the neighborhood supermarket, for instance, demonstrates how many goods are identical: most sweets are presented in similar packets, contain the same components, and are indistinguishable from one another when in contact. It is not surprising that the first brand to call attention to a distinction gains a significant competitive edge. This differentiator might simply be a brand extension that redefines the market or adds a new, significant

purchasing criterion. Brand extensions will offer a wealth of chances for present features to expand significantly as well as for new features that enhance product flexibility and even higher reliability (Innolytics, 2021).

Extensions may offer even more comprehensive product functionality by integrating new features that cut beyond product category limits. Effective brand extensions disrupt value chains and have the potential to alter the organization of an industry or a particular product category. Businesses are consequently compelled to reevaluate the fundamentals of competitiveness and everything they do on the inside to properly adjust to new chances and dangers to compete. Businesses often choose a smaller slice of a vast market, to the detriment of a wide slice of a smaller pie. This is justified by the idea that a sizable market offers limitless opportunity for expansion. But huge opportunities tend to encourage poor planning (Ishihara & Moorthy 2018).

Such firms pass up the potential to advertise where to play and how to win. It becomes challenging to choose who to contact and what consumers want from an undifferentiated business plan, though, because everyone is a prospective customer. Brand extensions present more limited economic options that, along with market expansion, necessitate the creation of a workable value proposition by the organization. In other words, brand extensions emphasize the necessity for strategic distinctiveness from the ground up. In these situations, performance also depends on the main brand's value proposition (Janskova, Kral & Krizanova 2018).

If the parent brand's value proposition is functional, there is little room for expansion. The biggest problem with brand extensions is how frequently they help provide a fleeting competitive advantage. On the other hand, a benefit of brand extensions is that strategic difference can transform brand extensions into a tool for competitive strategy. Even better, brand extensions become an unbeatable source of difference once they are included in the right competitive strategy framework. In a competitive framework, extensions get a head jump on the process of creating and maintaining a long-term competitive advantage (Munteanu, 2015).

Competitive Strategy

For businesses to be profitable over the long term, a definite competitive edge must be created and maintained. In the quest for a competitive advantage, businesses may struggle to create certain talents and to acquire the resources to protect these capabilities. Developing commercial relationships enables clients who are hesitant or unwilling to use competitors, maintaining a competitive edge. According to popular belief, only companies with a clear marketing orientation may create such relationships. If a company has mastered the skill of listening to customers, satisfies their demands superior to competitors, and values client loyalty, it has a good marketing orientation (Jin, Wang, Yu 2015).

As a result, firms spend a lot of money implementing or maintaining this marketing attitude. Businesses today succeed better by going against customer preferences and "shaping" consumer behavior. Competitive advantage cannot be sustained by consistently raising the bar on established success or distinguishing metrics. Today's market leaders are those who define what a product category's success or differentiation signifies. The ability of senior management to consider and handle competition is represented by the competitive advantage. CEOs frequently work to maximize the market's power (Juniarti & Afiff, 2020).

What most CEOs miss is the obvious truth that market domination equates to long-term profitability. Sustainable profitability is thus turning into the cost of competing. For better sales margins, however, competition is more intense than ever. Strategy should revolve around deliberate decision-making and being distinctive. But as companies are compelled to compete, this is getting harder. Corporations typically consider competitive advantage when creating new or better products. Businesses naturally keep tabs on their competitors to develop these products (MBAskool, 2020).

But in the era of hyper-competition, when companies start an unprecedented race to raise the bar on qualities or benefits, every product makes a promise to its customers to be bigger, better, or better. Ironically, customers eventually have more advantages than they want or need. It makes sense that brand loyalty is waning, and that any new product feels similar. Therefore, "What else can we do for our customers?" is no longer a key concern. The economy and consumers are now jointly at the core of business. Competitor differentiation should therefore be the basis of a strategic strategy, whilst rivalry should be the core of a marketing orientation. According to some academics, this is only possible if a firm does not try to broaden the name. Brand extensions eventually

aid in strategy forgetting because they increase brand associations rather than limiting brand emphasis (Meyvis, Golfsmith, & Dhar, 2012).

Quality

When brand extensions are introduced, customers' favorable expectations of quality will be leveraged. These brand extensions will use the brand identity to reach a new product group. It is asserted that high-quality brands can gain more recognition and expand farther than low-quality ones. Positively perceived brand consistency might facilitate brand launch. Extensions, as the highly respected brand is likely to elevate the associated goods in popularity. The apparent value of a brand in comparison to competitors is said to be a major factor affecting a business' performance, thus if the parent brand's quality is regarded as good, this transfer is also very beneficial for businesses. A large association that is positive about the brand's worth has an impact on how a brand expansion is evaluated (Alavinasab, Soltani, & Alimohammadi, 2017).

A brand's perceived quality refers to how consumers perceive its overall worth, superiority, or first recognition. One of the important elements that might influence a product's success and improve professional outcomes is quality perception. Businesses start to diversify their product offerings, which elevates the position of brand quality in the marketplace. Customers' opinions of the extended brand have been found to be impacted using distinctive brand names (also known as the parent brand) for product expansions. The more highly consumers rate the effectiveness of the parent brand, the more highly they rate the extended brand (Juniarti & Afiff, 2020). Customers' awareness of a brand's quality encourages the development of the brand's reputation. Real quality and perceived quality both have an impact on a brand's image. However, the former's impact is more significant than the latter. In addition to spending money on the product's physical quality, many businesses frequently invest a sizable amount of money in raising consumers' perceptions of the brand's quality. Brands with a high-quality reputation will expand their product offerings in various areas, in contrast to those with a poor reputation (Taqi & Muhammad, 2020).

Perceived Fit

The idea of similarity between product groups is just as clearly defined and measured as the more ethereal and challenging to define symbolic similarity between the parent brand and the new product. A new product category matches with an existing brand name if there appears to be a tie at the level of precise attributes, based on mental descriptions, or based on personality factors (Moons & Pelsmacker, 2015).

The ability of a product to adhere to the brand description constitutes the fit. The fit between the parent brand and the new product is representative and cannot depend on the resemblance of product features if managers aim to grow their brand to a new group far from the leading product. This fit with a basis will be delivered by brand identity (Viot, 2011).

The degree of similarity between the extensions and the core brand's customer experience is what determines how comparable they are. The degree of match between an extension and its parent brand is a key determinant of the performance of the extension, according to solid evidence from multiple aspects evaluated (Ramakrishnan, 2020).

During the past two decades, studies have found that perceived threat has a significant impact on customer behaviour and is instantly employed in marketing. A fundamental idea in consumer behaviour, perceived risk refers to how consumers view a product, their hesitancy before making a purchase, and the potential cost that could result from doing so. The customer's opinion of the brand's expansion, which encompasses new categories, is crucial to the success of the extension (Evangeline & Ragel, 2015).

Similarity relates to the consumer's perception that a product's expansion will make it more like the original brand, which will have both better and negative effects on customers. In fact, it is assumed that if the new product meets higher standards than the brand's original items, the expansion of the brand will result in greater results. The spread of the brand is influenced by how comparable the products are judged to be (Shabbir, 2020). This determines the core of the parent brand. A brand expansion strategy that involves risk is referred to as perceived risk. A multidimensional buyer is assumed to be undecided about purchasing a commodity. This

uncertainty often has two components: the potential repercussions of making a mistaken purchase and the uncertainty surrounding the outcomes if the goods is purchased (Sudaryanto, Courvisanos, & Rahayu, 2018).

The success of extensions depends, among other things, on how well the parent brand and its expanded brand align. However, in consumer brand assessments, both the literal fit regarding the brand and the client as well as the fit between a brand and its expansion might be important. Consumers value items for their capacity for self-expression and utilize symbolic brand definitions to identify and convey their true or desired personalities. (Ramakrishan, 2020)

Brands bear representative connotations. Brand personality is a key factor in symbolic brand importance. Even though there are infrequent differences between brands in terms of qualities and benefits, it is a vast phenomenon described as the collection of brand-related social character behaviors that distinguish brands in consumers' eyes. As a result, variations in self-brand personality can have a big impact on how brands are evaluated and how far they extend. Customers may consider different self-brand personality changes based on the situation (such as the extension's nature) (Moons & Pelsmacker, 2015).

The degree of similarity between a product extension's category and the brand itself and has two dimensions is known as apparent fitting. While the alignment between the brand image and the extension product classification is the brand-level acceptable, the fit of the product category represents the resemblance between the extension category and the parent brand's current product categories (Skyword 2014).

Customers' sentiments toward the expansion are influenced by perceived fit in two different ways. It can either accommodate the comparative impact of the brand's and category's approaches on the extension's attitude, or it can reconcile the change from the parent brand and extension group to the new extension of attitude components. This evolution of brand extension attitudes influences customer behaviour in terms of goals, preferences, and repeat purchases in the marketplace, and is therefore a crucial factor in determining whether brand extension will be successful (Alavinasab, Soltani, & Alimohammadi, 2017).

Innovation

Innovations undoubtedly contribute to the economy's continued growth, the rise of living standards, and the advancement of civilization. Innovation is seen as a key factor in productivity and economic growth. New products, utility models, brands, and entrepreneurial endeavors have a key role in the socioeconomic realities of the present. Innovation is frequently seen as an economic stimulant. Innovation's production varies from one company to the next and from one country to the next due to a variety of reasons (Moons & Pelsmacker, 2015).

Today's businesses are driven by innovation and brand value, and innovation is a key determinant of brand equity. Product innovation and brand value are acknowledged as crucial strategic assets that contribute significantly to the development and success of businesses. The development of values is supported by creativity. Clients prefer to buy products with strong brand equity over those with low brand equity (Shabbir, 2020).

When a brand has strong equity and customers are confident in the product's quality, it fosters favorable and advantageous relationships. This increases the business's faith in its capabilities to build successful customer relationships and its goods. High brand value also gives a company a lasting competitive advantage by giving customers a strong incentive to pay more for that brand. Different product categories may have different relationships between product innovation and brand strategy. The stronger an idea's impact on brand equity, the more disruptive it is. The brand portfolio's strategy determines the company's ability to innovate (Janoková, Kral, & Krizanová, 2018).

Human evolution has been the history of innovation, with people looking for new ways to satisfy their wants through the development, use, and exchange of inventive technologies. Innovation, however, is now a major force behind economic growth in modern free market economies due to advancements in information and communication technologies. Innovation does not always have to be completely original; it might make use of something that already exists. information or the resolution of an alternative issue or circumstance in an alternative circumstance. Innovation is the transition of already existing knowledge and ideas into a new or

enhanced consumer good that benefits the customer. Innovation is a strategy for bringing about changes that will increase the value of the product for the consumer while also raising awareness of the innovation adopter. Within an organization, innovation takes place at various levels, including management teams, departments, project teams, and even citizens. The capacity to identify and capitalize on connections between, obviously, two or more disparate facts drives innovation. It depends on a variety of factors that have an impact on every step of the process, from concept generation to production to implementation. The four pillars of creativity are collaboration, invention, execution, and value generation (Meyvis, Golfsmith, & Dhar, 2012).

Brand Loyalty

Research on consumer reactions to brand extensions has been developed based on their responses and associations with the brand. The type of the consumer-brand relationship influences their decisions regarding brand extensions. This has been demonstrated to be true, especially when there is a good fit between the extended product and the brand. Buyers respond favorably to brand extensions and make purchasing decisions when there is good and moderate coherence between the core product and the extended product (Sudaryanto, Courvisanos, & Rahayu, 2018).

Buyers' attitudes about brand extensions are influenced by brand trustworthiness rather than coherence. When there is good harmony, customers give positive feedback about brand extensions to their environment and are more willing to overlook any mistakes (Ergin & Sahin, 2015). Consumer innovation refers to a person's openness to new ideas as well as their willingness to experiment with new products and brands. People with high levels of creativity tend to be more entrepreneurial and more likely to experiment with new brands, according to a typical study (Evangeline & Ragel, 2015).

Innovation is a personality trait linked to buyers' eagerness to try out novel products. Consumers with high degrees of inventiveness also rigorously evaluate products for brand extension (Sudaryanto, Courvisanos, & Rahayu, 2018). Customers employ this symbolic meaning of products, and more specifically, brand personality, in many ways. Customers seek products that portray their true selves or ideal selves. Self-congruity will be guided by either the need for self-consistency and self-uncertainty or the desire for self-esteem and self-enhancement. The need to express one is authentic self-motivates both the evaluation and use of brands. Consumers use brands to manage, signal, preserve, and check their identities against others and themselves. To satisfy this need for self-consistency and self-continuity, customers frequently choose companies that share several personality traits with them (Moons & Pelsmacker, 2015).

Methodology

Data collection, Population and Sample Size

The primary source of data gathering was used in this research investigation. Primary data is information acquired directly from sources, i.e., when study is done to gather as much information as possible about the subject. Close-ended questionnaires on a 5-point Likert scale were used to collect the primary data for this thesis. The close-ended questions were self-administered, meaning that the researcher sent them directly to the respondents and then collected them back from them. The customers of Nestle products in Karachi, Pakistan, were the primary subject of the research study. The main goal of this research is to better understand the various factors that affect a brand's personality by using brand extensions created by Nestle, Pakistan. The population of this research study includes of nationwide customers of Nestle products in Pakistan. It would be impossible to interview every client because nestle caters to the mass market. As a result, 214 Nestle Pakistan customers will be included in our sample size because of their comments. We will use an online strategy on Google forms to contact consumers (the sample) to collect the replies. Convenience sampling was used in this study because there were few resources available. The researcher will contact respondents when it is most convenient by using online questionnaires. To ensure that the data gathered is accurate, at least 214 respondents were chosen for the study.

Findings and Discussion

Since ancient times, brand extensions have existed in the market. The decision to launch a new brand or product under the brand's umbrella is entirely up to the brand. This is carried out after a thorough analysis of all the elements influencing the brand's personality.

Success of a brand extension depends on how well-known the parent brand is in the marketplace. Even if the extended brand is a failure, its sales don't significantly affect those of the parent brand. Regarding Nestle in particular, the brand has several brand extensions under its wing. The vast majority of Nestle's brand expansions have been global successes, which has helped to maintain the brand's popularity and the brand loyalty of its customers.

This study, which is conducted on Nestle, Pakistan, focuses on the effect of brand extension on brand personality. This thesis provides in-depth understandings of brand personality and brand expansions. The independent variables for brand extension considered in this research study include competitive strategy, quality, perceived fit, innovation, and brand loyalty. The dependent variable is brand personality. Each independent variable's unique effect on the dependent variable was examined. All of the initial research hypotheses were confirmed, demonstrating that all brand extension elements significantly affect the brand personality. This thesis provides a thorough investigation of how parent brands can preserve their characteristics while growing their brands. There are some brand extension variables that affect brand personality. The effect of every element; Brand was examined for competitive strategy, quality, perceived fit, innovation, and brand loyalty. Personality. Only if the brand's value is increased will consumers purchase from brand extensions. In the market, personality is well-maintained. If the parent brand has a poor reputation, the extended brand could also be a failure. Even the brand extension may occasionally have an impact on the brand's reputation by causing consumers to switch to other brands for a variety of reasons, but most crucially, cost and excellence.

This study focuses mostly on the brand personality and how the brand extension affects that personality. different brand extension criteria, including brand loyalty, perceived fit, perceived quality, and competition strategy. When extending a brand, the preferences of the consumer have always been respected. All of the factors considered in this study are related to brand extension. Using the SPSS software, regression analysis is used to examine the relationship between two or more variables. Understanding the nature of the link between variables is made easier by the regression analysis. The association between variables, whether it be positive or negative, was also examined using the Pearson's Correlation test.

The Pearson's Correlation analysis performed using SPSS software has the following results. According to the results, the correlation coefficient of "Brand Extension" on "Brand Personality" is 0.328 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 32.8%. The correlation coefficient of "Competitive Strategy" on "Brand Personality" is 0.185 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 18.5%. The correlation coefficient of "Quality" on "Brand Personality" is 0.153 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 15.3%. The correlation coefficient of "Perceived Fit" on "Brand Personality" is 0.247 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 24.7%. The correlation coefficient of "Innovation" on "Brand Personality" is 0.071 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 7.1%. The correlation coefficient of "Brand Loyalty" on "Brand Personality" is 0.068 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that there is a significant positive association between the two variables of 6.8%.

Similarly, the results of the regression analysis showed a similar picture, where "Brand Extension" has a regression coefficient of 0.413 with "Brand Personality". This means that an increase of 1 unit in "Brand Extension" will bring about an increase of 0.413 units in "Brand Personality". The t-value associated with this relationship is 9.602, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that "Brand Extension" has a significant impact on "Brand Personality".

“Competitive Strategy” has a regression coefficient of 0.458 with “Brand Personality”. This means that an increase of 1 unit in “Competitive Strategy” will bring about an increase of 0.458 units in “Brand Personality”. The t-value associated with this relationship is 11.733, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that “Competitive Strategy” has a significant impact on “Brand Personality”.

“Quality” has a regression coefficient of 0.235 with “Brand Personality”. This means that an increase of 1 unit in “Quality” will bring about an increase of 0.235 units in “Brand Personality”. The t-value associated with this relationship is 6.878, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that “Quality” has a significant impact on “Brand Personality”.

“Perceived Fit” has a regression coefficient of 0.325 with “Brand Personality”. This means that an increase of 1 unit in “Perceived Fit” will bring about an increase of 0.325 units in “Brand Personality”. The t-value associated with this relationship is 7.219, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that “Perceived Fit” has a significant impact on “Brand Personality”.

“Innovation” has a regression coefficient of 0.259 with “Brand Personality”. This means that an increase of 1 unit in “Innovation” will bring about an increase of 0.259 units in “Brand Personality”. The t-value associated with this relationship is 7.101, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that “Innovation” has a significant impact on “Brand Personality”.

“Brand Loyalty” has a regression coefficient of 0.446 with “Brand Personality”. This means that an increase of 1 unit in “Brand Loyalty” will bring about an increase of 0.446 units in “Brand Personality”. The t-value associated with this relationship is 6.542, which is greater than 2, with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that “Brand Loyalty” has a significant impact on “Brand Personality”.

Based on these results all alternate hypotheses (H1-H6) are accepted.

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